

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

KINETIC REGULARITIES OF ETHYLBENZENE OXIDATION AND DECOMPOSITION OF α -PHENYLETHYL HYDROPEROXIDE IN THE PRESENCE OF THE CATIONIC SURFACTANT

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Abstract

Kinetic regularities of ethylbenzene (RH) oxidation and decomposition of α -phenylethylhydroperoxide (ROOH) in the presence of the cationic surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) have been studied. As the amount of decomposed hydroperoxide exceeds the surfactant amount by more than one order of magnitude, CTAB can be considered as a catalyst of hydroperoxide decomposition of ethylbenzene oxidation.

Analysis of ethylbenzene oxidation products showed that hydroperoxide, acetophenone and methylphenylcarbinol are formed in the presence of DTAB. The estimation of temperature coefficient of decomposition rate of ROOH in the presence of DTAB gives the value of effective activation energy $E_{ef.} = 50,2$ kJ/mol, which is considerably lower than the activation energy of thermal decomposition of ROOH $E_{ef.} = 104$ kJ/mol. Cationic DTAB promotes charge separation and hydroperoxide decomposition by bond. In an oxygen atmosphere such decomposition leads to formation of peroxy radicals and acceleration of free-radical oxidation of ethylbenzene.

The nature and scale of the influence of heterogeneity and kinetic nonuniformity of the medium, on kinetics and mechanism of ethylbenzene oxidation and decomposition of hydroperoxideethylbenzene in the presence of CPAB is revealed.

Keywords: surfactants, ethylbenzene, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, hydroperoxide, microheterogeneity.

INTRODUCTION

The oxidation of hydrocarbons by molecular oxygen is one of the most attractive areas of petrochemical synthesis: peroxides, ketones, acids and other oxygen-containing products. On the other hand, the actual problem is the protection of organic materials such as food and industrial oils, fuels, cosmetics and others from thermal-oxidative degradation under the influence of air oxygen. The scientific basis for the control of oxidation processes is the theory of liquid-phase oxidation, developed as applied to homogeneous and heterogeneous processes. However, many real systems are microheterogeneous, water-organic or become so in the process of operation [1-5]. Surfactant additives regulate the microstructures of the medium, prevent the release of water dissolved and formed during oxidation. The effect of surfactants on the oxidizability of hydrocarbon substrates is practically unexplored, although a priori can be expected significant effects related to the possibility of association of surfactants and oxidation products containing polar oxygen-containing groups, the involvement of inhibitors including hydrophilic fragments in these associations and consequently changes in their reactivity and even directions of reactions involving these compounds [6-10].

Additives of ionogenic surfactants (surfactants) catalytically affect hydroperoxide decomposition and hydrocarbon oxidation [7-15]. In the presence of surfactants can change not only the speed of the process, but also the composition of the resulting products, i.e. the direction of the reaction. The nature of the effect differs for cationic and anionic surfactants, depends on the nature of the oxidised hydrocarbon and the resulting

hydroperoxide, as well as on the structure of the hydrocarbon fragment of the surfactant [15-18]. On the example of ethylbenzene (RH) oxidation and decomposition of phenylethylhydroperoxide (ROOH) we have found that catalysis of ROOH decomposition in the presence of an anionic surfactant - sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) [8] and cationic acetyltrimethylammonium bromide (DTAB) [9] is connected with their colloidal properties, namely, it is connected with the formation of joint surfactant-ROOH aggregates of the reverse micelle type, in which the peroxide bond decomposition becomes easier. DDS catalyses heterolytic decomposition of ROOH. In recent years, surfactants or, as they are often called, phase transport catalysts (PTs) have been widely used in various catalytic processes. The work [21-22] gives a large amount of information about the influence of surfactants of different structure (cationic, anionic, non-ionic) on the absorption rate of oxygen during the oxidation of tetralin, cumene and cyclohexene. In the presence of most cationic surfactants the absorption rate of oxygen is increased. Anionic surfactants in the form of acids increase the rate of oxygen uptake while their sodium salts slightly inhibit oxidation. In the two-phase system, the cationic surfactant activity is greatly reduced in the presence of water as a separate phase. It is noted that the presence of hydroperoxides is essential for OP catalysed oxidation of hydrocarbons. In this case, cationic and anionic surfactants react with more nucleophilic (internal) and more electrophilic (external) hydroperoxide O-atom correspondingly, thus facilitating homolysis of O-O-bond. Non-ionic surfactants affect the rate of hydroperoxide decomposition through the formation of H-bonds [20-23].

Combined action of metal compounds of variable valence and surfactants is of great interest, since such compositions can regulate the process speed in a wide range. A number of such compositions have been studied in relation to emulsion oxidation of cumene and other hydrocarbons [21-24].

The purpose of this work is to study cationic surfactant - cetyltrimethylammonium bromide on ethylbenzene oxidation and hydroperoxide-phenylethyl decomposition.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Oxidation of ethylbenzene was carried out at 60°C in a barbotage-type reactor with a reverse cooler in a current of air or oxygen, hydroperoxide decomposition - at 50-90°C in a current of high-purity nitrogen or air (1.6 l/h). Peroxide concentration was determined iodometrically. The rate of oxygen absorption was measured on gasometric device at constant pressure of O₂, equal to 0.1 MPa.

Products of ethylbenzene oxidation and hydroperoxide decomposition were analyzed by chromatomass-

spectrometry (GC-MS). Conditions of analysis were similar [3].

Ethylbenzene (OAO Nizhnekamskneftekhim) was purified by the generally accepted procedure [19]. Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (Serva) was used without additional purification. An ultrasonic dispersant was used for dissolution of DTAB in hydrocarbon medium.

Results and discussion

In the absence of O₂, the introduction of DTAB dramatically increased the rate of RON consumption. At 120 °C the effective rate constant of RON decomposition in the presence of 10 mM DTAB increases more than 500 times, at 90°C - 1800 times (Fig.1). At the same time, in atmosphere oxygen in the presence of DTAB an increase of ROOH concentration is observed with a considerably higher rate than at ethylbenzene autoxidation, which contains the same amount of hydroperoxide initially (fig. 1, cr. 1,2). In the presence of DTAB, the hydroperoxide decomposition to free radicals is accelerated, which leads to an increase in the chain initiation (w_i) rate and the process as a whole.

Fig. 1. Kinetic curves of ROOH accumulation and consumption without additives (1,1'), in the presence of DTAB (2,2') and TEAB (3,3') in O₂ (1',2',3') and N₂(1',2',3'); 90°C, [ROOH]₀ = 50 mM

Additives of tetraethylammonium bromide (TEAB) having no long-chain alkyl substituent practically don't influence on ROOH decomposition in N₂ atmosphere and its accumulation under oxidation conditions (Fig.1 cr.3,3'). It means that Br⁻ ion does not take part in ROON reduction directly and suggests that catalytic effect of DTAB is connected with its colloidal properties.

$$\frac{d[ROOH]}{dt}(O_2) = \frac{k_p}{\sqrt{2k_t}} [RH] \cdot \sqrt{w_i} - k_{\phi} \cdot [ROOH] \quad (II)$$

where k_p is the rate constant of continuation (k₃), k_t is the rate constant of chain breaking (k₄), w_i = e^{-k_{ef}[ROOH]} - rate of chain initiation, k_{ef} - effective rate constant of ROOH decay, e - radical output during

The rate of ROON accumulation in the O₂ atmosphere and its degradation in N₂ are equal:

$$-\frac{d[ROOH]}{dt}(N_2) = k_{\phi} \cdot [ROOH] \quad (I)$$

ROOH decay. Assuming at 90°C and from the experimental values of the reaction rates (Fig. 3), we obtain e = 0.2 from equations (I-II).

Assessment of the temperature coefficient of decomposition rate of ROON in the presence of DTAB

gives the value of effective activation energy $E_f \sim 50.2$ kJ/mol, which is significantly lower than the activation energy of thermal decomposition of ROOH (104 kJ/mol), known from literature.

Analysis of ethylbenzene oxidation products by GC-MS showed that practically the same products are

Thus, cationic DTAB promotes charge separation and hydroperoxide decomposition at the bond. In an oxygen atmosphere such decomposition leads to the formation of peroxy radicals and accelerated free-radical oxidation of ethyl benzene. In an inert atmosphere non-analyzable by GC method polymer products are formed, apparently. Styrene or styrene oxide can be assumed to be the monomer.

Conclusion

It follows from the data obtained that the cationic DTAB has a significant influence on the oxidation rate of RH and the key reaction, the rate and probably the mechanism of which changes in the presence of DTAB, is the degradation of ROOH which determines under auto-oxidation conditions.

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